

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: The specific features and current problems of the use of modern digital technologies in the educational system today are discussed, which shows that distance education has become an integral part of the entire educational process. Also, problems arise, some of which the author tries to analyze. It is one of the important terms in the field of modern education, which highlighted the actual aspects and importance of using digital technologies on a theoretical basis and gave its recommendations.

Key words: digital technologies, modern education, distance education, problems of educational implementation.

Introduction: In the modern world, the development and improvement of the higher education system is increasingly dependent on digital technologies. Digital technologies allow not only to make the educational process more effective and interactive, but also provide ample opportunities for students to acquire new knowledge. The rapid growth of distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic has forced educational institutions to adopt new pedagogical approaches and implement digital technologies.

This process has fundamentally changed the way teachers teach, the systems of creating and presenting learning materials, and the communication between students and teachers. Digital technologies, including virtual classrooms, electronic libraries, interactive textbooks and educational platforms, play an important role in improving the quality of education.

At the same time, the introduction of digital technologies requires updating the technical capabilities of higher education institutions, pedagogical practices and educational management structures. In the introductory part of this article, we discuss the role of digital technologies in the higher education system, how they can affect the quality of education and how they can change the future educational processes.

Reasoning: The development and improvement of the higher education system in modern society is increasingly dependent on digital technologies. Digital technologies allow to make the educational process more effective and interactive, and at the same time, provide students with ample opportunities to acquire new knowledge.

The Role of Digital Technologies in Education

Digital technologies have the potential to fundamentally change the pedagogical approaches of educational institutions, the systems of creating and presenting educational materials, as well as the communication

between students and teachers. They play an important role in improving the quality of education through, inter alia, virtual classrooms, electronic libraries, interactive textbooks and educational platforms.

Advantages and Disadvantages of Digital Technologies:

The advantages of digital technologies in education are clear: they provide an opportunity to learn independently of time and space, provide easy access to educational materials, help personalize the learning process, and increase the quality of education. However, at the same time, the implementation of digital technologies can also cause some disadvantages, such as technical problems, insufficient skills of teachers in the use of technologies, or low digital literacy of students.

The Future of Digital Technologies in Education

The future of digital technology in education looks bright. They enable educational institutions to adopt new pedagogical approaches, update educational management structures, and improve the quality of education. At the same time, the introduction of digital technologies requires updating the technical capabilities of higher education institutions, pedagogical practices and educational management structures.

The current technologies are not just a trend, but are gaining importance as the main means of development. In Uzbekistan, education, health care and public services are being digitized step by step. The implementation of electronic government projects in the field of public administration allows to simplify bureaucratic processes, increase transparency and activate citizen participation.

In the rapidly changing landscape of the 21st century, the large-scale introduction of digital technologies into life and the rapid development of artificial intelligence are reshaping the global paradigm of the world. This technological revolution creates great opportunities for developing countries like Uzbekistan.

Global talking points today include innovation management and the introduction of digitization in higher education. By combining and balancing these factors, digitization can be the key to increasing the innovative capacity of higher education and increasing the use of advanced educational technologies in curricula. This, in the end, increases the level of knowledge acquisition by students.

Research in the field shows that digitization is critical for higher education. Because it demonstrates a high level of reliability with the "Industry 4.0" system. The integration of digital technologies, the use of the Internet and digital public services has a significant impact on higher education in our country.

The challenges of human capital required in the digital economy are at the center of research on innovation and digitization in higher education. Worldwide, digitization has changed the entire structure of education in the last decade. Practitioners, scientists and politicians began to pay serious attention to the development of education. Many traditional education models and teaching methods are becoming obsolete as global living and working standards are updated as a result of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Digital education permeates all aspects of our social and economic life, primarily helping students to learn remotely.

The term "digitalization" refers to a business strategy supported by trends related to the use of digital technologies in all areas of human society. The growth of smart cities and objects is connected with the increase of digitalization as one of the main topics in the world, and it is one of the main factors of the development of modern countries. The fourth industrial revolution emphasizes the use of high-speed Internet to facilitate the reception of information in digital form. As the process of expanding the economy through digital technologies moves faster, the higher education system is changing its international, marketing, financial and economic activities in order to remain competitive in the global educational services market. Digitization in education opens up new opportunities for learning to use technologies and increases the efficiency of resource use.

Educational collaborations are moving beyond advanced and non-traditional approaches to digital learning. It is time to include digitization in the competitiveness strategy of the educational institution, as well as in the educational policy of the state. Today, students around the world are used to using digital devices such as smartphones, tablets and laptops at all levels from primary school to higher education. Many people use gadgets for communication and entertainment. However, the changing world demands that young people learn and be educated through these technologies.

Conclusions and Recommendations: The introduction of digital technologies in the higher education system is important in improving the quality of education and adapting the educational process to modern requirements. Digital technologies enable educational institutions to adopt new pedagogical approaches, update educational management structures, and improve the quality of education.

Digital technologies allow not only to make the educational process more effective and interactive, but also provide ample opportunities for students to acquire new knowledge. However, at the same time, the implementation of digital technologies can also cause some disadvantages, such as technical problems, insufficient skills of teachers in the use of technologies, or low digital literacy of students.

In the future, the role of digital technologies in education is expected to become more important. They enable educational institutions to adopt new pedagogical approaches, update educational management structures, and improve the quality of education. At the same time, the introduction of digital technologies requires updating the technical capabilities of higher education institutions, pedagogical practices and educational management structures.

The future of digital technology in education looks bright. They enable educational institutions to adopt new pedagogical approaches, update educational management structures, and improve the quality of education. At the same time, the introduction of digital technologies requires updating the technical capabilities of higher education institutions, pedagogical practices and educational management structures.

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